

Mobile game-based learning in cultural heritage education: a bibliometric analysis

Mobile games
for cultural
heritage
teaching

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this study was to analyze the state of mobile game-based learning in the field of cultural heritage education.

Design/methodology/approach – A bibliometric methodology based on scientific mapping and an analysis of co-words was used. The scientific production on this field of study indexed in Scopus was analyzed. The analysis included a total of 725 publications.

Findings – The results show that the National Research Council of Italy is the institution with the highest volume of production. Among the journals, the Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage stands out. In addition, in the analysis of the structural and thematic development of co-words, a low percentage of keyword matching was observed. The research is currently mainly oriented to pedagogical methods, especially game-based learning, gamification and the use of serious games, although these are not the only trends in this field. Research is also focusing on virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality.

Originality/value – This work is an exploratory and novel study that analyzes the publications to date on mobile game-based learning in cultural heritage education. In theoretical terms, this can serve as support so that other researchers interested in this field can access the information highlighted in this work. From a practical perspective, this work will contribute to the promotion of new innovative actions in cultural heritage education to satisfy the demands of a learning group increasingly familiar with games technology.

Keywords Bibliometric analysis, Scientific mapping, Mobile learning, Game-based learning, Video games, Heritage education

Paper type Literature review

1. Introduction

The field of education is evolving to meet the new challenges related to the competencies of the professionals of the future and the demands of a new generation of learners that is immersed in the digital world from birth (Díaz *et al.*, 2019). Mobile game-based learning is one of the emerging methods that have the potential to reach these objectives.

Mobile game-based learning is a method that focuses on the application of digital games and game-based apps in education and training through mobile devices (Krouska *et al.*, 2022).

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